

THE GOVERNING EQUATIONS OF SURFACE VESSELS AND AQUATIC BODIES: WHY PEOPLE GET IT WRONG?

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ABSTRACT

Currently, the motion of ships and other surface vessels are described (governed) by certain equations which contain several assumptions. In the same manner, the movement of fish and other aquatic bodies (even submarines) are controlled by another set of governing equations with several assumptions. The chief and common assumption for both situations is that the rotation occurs around the mass centre. This assumption is wrong. The main point, in this analysis, centered around the rotation point of these bodies introduces an error of hundreds if not thousands percent in certain cases. The added properties were neglected in the early studies of these movements up to 198x. Later, the added properties were gradually added to the analysis. In all the cases examined, the analysis assumes that the rotation of these bodies is all the time around the body mass centre. In other words, under this assumption unconstrained ship/fish exposed to a force will rotate around the ship/fish centre. This fundamentally wrong and introduced so large error in many cases into the computation and that probably render the research work worthless. The possible causes of this entrenched assumption are presented. Additionally, the three categories of the of rotation centres are described.

Key Words

Ship Rotation Axes, Yaw, Roll, Pitch, Added Mass, Added Moment of Inertia, Virtual Added Properties, Marine Navigation, Fish Locomotion

1 Introduction

The marine navigation and stability has attracted very talented individuals to solve these problems. The research in these areas,

advance the perturbation methods and many other mathematical and numerical areas. Yet, the changes experienced in the field are very interesting. Until the 1980s the added properties were basically ignored yet people solved the problem and of course have abundantly convincing evidence and the most authoritative (experimental) proof for their calculations (Devin 1980). Nevertheless, once one realizes that these works were erroneous the added properties were included in the calculations. No work that was surveyed mentioned this wonderful and convincing experimental evidence of ignoring the added properties as if they vanished and were never published or appeared in the past.

An unconstrained rigid body rotates about its mass centre when force is applied on any location on the body. This concept was applied to ships and swimming bodies. The history of applying the center of rotation started with looking at rolling as it is easiest to visualize and the most intuitive. The roll investigation is related to ship stability in static conditions where the smallest dimension is rotating. Bouguer, the father of the analytical ship stability, invented the metacenter, and this point was considered as the rotation hinge of the ship (see for example see youtube video <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XJU7ACOKjYI> by Dr. Laura K. Alford lecture University of Michigan). During that time, a solution of the second order differential equation made its appearance (Froude 1861) (Notice that today a different method is used to solve second order ODE). The fact is that the metacenter has nothing to do with rotation started to penetrate into some circles of the ship stability and ship navigation community. For example, a summary of of mass centre advocacy was described (Lewandowski 2004). The treatment of ship rotation around the metacenter was substituted by the rotation around the mass centre. It should be noted that there

were individuals from prominent institutions such as MIT who claimed that rotation can be either or (not clear how physically this dual rotations possible and it will left for them to explain). Yes, these claims appeared in the literature.

Vossers was the one of the earliest (as far it was observed by this author) to realize the inconsistency in the governing equations. The logic of these arguments is based on the idea that if you have a system in isolation, the rotation has to be around the mass centre. It can be notice that the some of the development was like mammal living in dinosaur’s world. Johnsen (2022), while ignoring all the previously conducted works, concluded that the added mass combined with ship mass constitutes the system (rigid body) and hence determines the rotation point. One only can wonder why people (scientists) do not carry literature review.

Several papers (a chain of papers) realized the rotation must in a different location but due to mathematical reasons. Vossers expanded several terms into Taylor’s series to create new governing equations (1962). It seems that physics was poorly understood and the model was not accepted. Balcer made another attempt (2004) which was a very strange argument based on shifting of the added mass. Since the equations were based on the manipulation and not based on physics, the model was ignored. Balcer mentioned another attempt by Bruce L. Hutchison (1991). The change of the rotation axis, according to Balcer, has different reasons such unclear experimental design and or mathematical manipulation.

FIGURE 1. The common names for the ship movements.

While several people noticed that the rotation point is not at the mass centre, the fact is that the change was noticed. Yet, it will be demonstrated below that Johnsen’s idea conflicts with the reality in the roll and pitch rotations (see fig. 2 for different hinge point under different scenarios). In the yaw rotation, there is no clear hinge point and calculations are required.

The first real idea was proposed by Laustrup (2011) in which he realized that the rotation is around point \mathcal{A} (“center” point on the liquid plain) for the rolling motion (see fig. 3). He

demonstrated the actual physics for the rotation. As a physicist he did not have a strong influence on marine engineers and this idea basically was ignored. This author redeveloped independently the rotation point in 2016–2017 (difference of 5 years) only later to find out about Laustrup’s idea was done first. The expansion of the proof is provided in this paper. The original derivation was done only for rolling while here it deals with any rotation where there is a significant change in liquid density. While the term “significant” is not defined and should be defined in a dimensional analysis context, it will be explained the book “Basics of Fluid Mechanics”. It can be noticed that the change does not have to be abrupt. Yet, Laustrup did not realize the significance of the change of the rotation point has on the governing equations. A discussion on the validity of the previous (Johnsen) idea is presented in the next section.

2 Fundamentals

It is commonly accepted that the moment or force applied to multiply bodies which are in isolation rotates the bodies around mass centre. This point will not be meticulously deliberated here since there numerous proofs for this scenario in numerous locations in the literature. A force that acts on an isolated rigid body in any location while all the masses in the system are bonded rigidly will be rotated the body around mass centre with an equivalent moment and force. In essence, the definition of the added mass of the ship means that ship is not isolated from the added mass. Hence, clearly the added mass must be part of the system.

For ship stability or marine navigation, the question is what system should be used. This question is cardinal and critical in writing the governing equation. The location of the mass centre not only affects the governing equations but also predicts the path of the ship or the marine (free surface) body, or the aquatic body will be traveling. The hinge or rotation point is not necessarily in same location as the body mass centre and even might not be on the ship body. To demonstrate this point consider two situations shown in fig. 2. Figure 2 exhibits a free body on the left (a) and a hinged body at point \mathcal{A} on the right (b). The free body on the left rotates around point \mathcal{G} while the body on the right rotates around point \mathcal{A} . This statement should not be controversial to most people. For the rolling and pitching of surface vehicles, the situation is identical. Yet, this statement does not seem analogous to most researchers. This paper is written to fix this knowledge hole.

The principles involved in ship rotation (movement) have to be examined. While the leading and the prominent scientists’ opinions (more of a religious believe and maybe an even better term to describe them is a cult exhibited by people who work in the field) is that the rotation must be at the ship mass centre. Up until to 30 years ago the dominant belief was that the added mass (please read properties) is irrelevant. Again since this belief is not based on scientific principles, the change happened and

FIGURE 2. Two situations of rotation a) a free body and b) a hinged body

this author cannot find the precise time or paper that triggered this change. Some showing that mass centre was used earlier like in (Abkowitz 1964) but it was not common approach. Once the change occurred, the added mass was adjoined and become part of the governing equation. In fact, in most papers dealing with ship navigation, fish locomotion etc have accepted the added mass (properties). In other words, while accepting that the added mass has to be part of the system (equations), nevertheless, at the same time they do not accept the added mass to be of the system mass for the centre calculations (or aquatic body), which is a schizophrenic line of thought. This common logic cannot be understood (how people are not accepting corrected ideas or do accept conflicting idea.).

Recently this author communicated with many researchers in fish locomotion and the ship navigation communities by posing this question those who used rotation around the mass centre “do you have any logic or proof or experiments properly conducted for using the ship’s centre?”. Apparently no one was able to provide an answer which is better than “everyone use this technique.” One expects more from individuals to profess to be scientists.

3 Difference Between the Rotations

Of the three rotations, the most studied is rolling (google scholar 5 million for roll 0.7 millions for pitch and 0.2 millions yaw). In navigation, this rotation is neglected while the logic for this assumption is questionable, nevertheless it can provide some understanding for other rotations more specifically for the pitch with a limited application for the yaw. The roll and pitch (see fig. 1) have a specific hinge point while the yaw has no such point. The reason for the change is the body displaces different liquid (different densities). For a body attached to a wall for example, there is a clear and well defined rotation point. This point is intuitively understood without any calculations of the mass centre for the combination of the wall and body. (Why? the mathematics is actually complicated. If you have a simpler expiation this author will love to learn about it.) There is no place in the

literature disputes this point of rotation or even attempt/suggest calculations. The same can be said for the mass–spring system in which the system clearly rotates around the equilibrium. The same is true for body in a variable density field either abrupt or not.

FIGURE 3. Possible point of rotation of floating body

Identical arguments apply to roll rotation. The equilibrium occurs around point \mathcal{A} and not around any other point. A full discussion on the equilibrium appeared in (Bar-Meir 2021). Figure 3 exhibits points \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{G} for a symmetrical body on which lay on the symmetry line. If rotation occurs on higher location than point \mathcal{A} such as point \mathcal{M} (not shown in the figure) than less of the cross section area will be submerged (less buoyancy). Hence, the rotation with a higher rotation point result in a force downward and a moment due to less buoyancy. On the other hand, if the rotation is below point \mathcal{A} the rotation will crate a force moving upward and moment. Rotation around the mass centre (below point \mathcal{A}), creates an unbalance force and moment. In other words, during the rotation the righting moment is applied with an unbalanced force. For these arguments, notice the change amount at the submerged area which change relationship between the ship weight and buoyancy. Since the physics dictates that Newton’s law must be obeyed, the force cannot be responded with a moment. Thus, the only possible rotation is around point \mathcal{A} . The rotation in the pitch direction has identical arguments, hence the rotation is in the same location. An additional point, Johnsen assumes/calculates that the mass centre for the combined system must “move” below the gravity and that is the new rotation point. This assumption is wrong based on the above arguments (moment cannot responded to by a force).

The yaw rotation is different for surface bodies because it does not change liquid densities. It can be noticed that the rotation point for aquatic bodies, the roll and the pitch are similar in the sense that there is a natural hinge point (must have gradual density change or two phases abrupt change). These rotation movements require some calculations and they are more complicated since the mass of the system (added mass) is unknown (it depends on the rotation point which is also unknown). If the added mass somehow miraculously was known, the location mass centre is not sufficient to determine because is location is also required. Admittedly, the solution proposed by this author

is not complete, even though some understanding was gained and yet may not be present at this stage.

4 Examine the Erroneous Methods

The most common and reasonable advocacy for the rotation around the mass centroid was raised by anonymous user (asked to remove his name) “the error is insignificant”. Consider the movement of the ship in a sway direction where the added mass is significantly larger than the ship mass (Bar-Meir 2022). In that case, the question at where is the mass centre of the added mass. The added mass is the only the representation of the acceleration of the liquid mass (sea water) by the volume of the (submerged) of the ship. In the literature, there no table and or information about the centroid of the added mass. Taking the minimalistic approach where the mass is assumed to be condensed and attached to the ship body (in reality the added mass spread according to the way added mass is defined or calculated). In perfect symmetry, the added mass will be attached head and behind in the symmetry and hence no change in that case location of the centre of the combined system. Nevertheless, the change can be very large when the body is not symmetrical for example in the case of fish movement where the body is not symmetrical.

According the above analysis when the ship undergoes rolling, the yaw rotation “sees” a unsymmetrical body (with the exception of a perfect cylinder at the center) even though the ship was symmetrical at equilibrium and thus the mass centre location changes. The following part is a bit speculative. A minimalistic approach suggests that when rolling is about 10° , the change in the centroid seem to be (this estimate is very crude and thus it is not presented and others are invited to provide better estimates) in the range of 12% of ship width. Thus, taking this number means the change of the total moment of inertia in the yaw direction is to be larger by about 25%. Now if the rolling coupled with pitching the total change in the mass centre can reach a larger amount and the moment of inertia to be double the original. In addition the added moment of inertia is a strong function of the draft. The interested reader will notice that this discussion means the regular pendulum became a double pendulum (this will be discussed in following papers). A change in the heave changes the added moment of inertia in the yaw direction. In another paper under preparation it will be shown that the change in the added mass is associated with large energy loss. The discussion on this effect is not present here.

Concluding Remarks

The classification of the rotation points was made for rigid body. There are basically three categories of rotation points: one) in a vacuum where the center of rotation is the body centre, two) on the body within two phases (example air/water) the rotation is located in point \mathcal{A} , and three) the last point for bodies in liq-

uid (plane) (surroundings) with considerable density. The explanation of the hinged point was enhanced as compared to what appears in public publication.

About the Author

As opposed to many other researchers, this author does not brag about how many citations his work has or jobs he held but only points to how many breakthroughs he has made. In the die casting industry, he has revolutionized the field by solving several major open questions. These questions include the critical plunger velocity, pQ^2 diagram, and critical vent area etc (for those who not familiar with die casting, these are the main pliers of die casting.). It has to be mentioned that the die casting establishment believed in solutions which violated the second law of the thermo and has spent millions promoting these beliefs (like the woke religion). Since the problems were not solved, literally hundreds of CFD teams from all over the world attempted to solve the problem in vain where this author solved them. The establishment fought against publishing these discoveries. The irony is that these author’s models today are undisputed and accepted in the industry.

Furthermore, the author solved several open problems in shock dynamics and potential of compressed substances. Additionally, this author solved the deep ocean pressure and speed of sound which many oceanographers failed to calculate (Pushka Equation) and which people like Sandip Ghosal from Northwestern university plagiarized. Ghosal is not the only one who copy Bar-Meir’s idea. The ship stability went major revision and basically revamped the field in particular the added mass (properties). The old governing equations yielding hundreds percent errors had to be modified due to discoveries of this author. When you search on Google and type “basics of fluid” it offers Genick Bar-Meir as first or second results. This fact is positive proof that the establishment efforts to silence this author have failed.

Conflict of Interest

The author Genick Bar-Meir certify that he has NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity or person with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent–licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials or individuals discussed in this manuscript.

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